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Valuing hunting as an ecosystem service: a national-level assessment using cost-based and benefit transfer methods in the Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Hunting provides both provisioning and cultural ecosystem services, yet its economic value remains underrepresented in natural capital accounting. This study presents the first comprehensive, national-level assessment of hunting-related ecosystem services in the Czech Republic. Using a combination of market price valuation, cost-based methods, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatial allocation, the analysis estimates the 2022 value of wild game meat and recreational hunting. Results show that recreational hunting generates CZK 9.33 billion (USD 677 million), while the value of game meat provision totals CZK 548 million (USD 39.7 million). The comparison of primary valuation and benefit transfer methods reveals substantial discrepancies, with transferred values overestimating provisioning services and underestimating recreational values. Values are spatially allocated to ecosystem types using CORINE land cover, making them compatible with the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA). The study presents an indicative methodological framework for valuing hunting-related ecosystem services and highlights the importance of context-specific data for informing natural capital accounting, and sustainable wildlife management.

1. Introduction

Hunting provides a range of ecosystem services that are crucial for human well-being. These include provisioning services, such as wild-sourced meat and animal by-products, as well as cultural services like recreational hunting and the maintenance of traditional practices. Particularly, forest ecosystems deliver substantial non-market services that are often undervalued in conventional economic assessments (Cori et al., 2025). International frameworks, including the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) (United Nations et al., 2021) and the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018), classify hunting primarily as a provisioning and cultural service. Hunting may also contribute to regulating services by influencing game populations and associated damage, but these effects are not explicitly treated as separate categories in SEEA-EA or CICES and are methodologically difficult to quantify. Accordingly, focusing on provisioning and cultural services provides a clear, internationally consistent foundation for assessing hunting's ecological, economic, and social roles.

However, game species can impose a range of costs on society, including damage to forests and agricultural crops, traffic accidents,

disease transmission, and impacts on biodiversity (Bissonette et al., 2008; Gren et al., 2018; Sáenz-de-Santa-María & Tellería, 2015; Turek et al., 2020; Valente et al., 2020). In the Czech Republic, mainly large ungulates such as red deer (*Cervus elaphus*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), and wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) are responsible for most of the forest and crop damage, with annual costs estimated at CZK 5–7 billion (Erber, 2019; Turek et al., 2020), although this figure does not capture all types of impacts. While hunting is expected to mitigate some of these costs, quantifying avoided damages requires detailed ecological and economic modelling.

Moreover, the distribution of benefits and costs is uneven: hunters capture private benefits through recreation and meat, whereas landowners and farmers often bear the financial and ecological burdens (Apollonio et al., 2017; Turek et al., 2020; Valente et al., 2020). Such imbalances have been widely documented across Europe, particularly in regions experiencing rising ungulate populations (Apollonio et al., 2017; Valente et al., 2020).

Economic valuation provides a well-established framework to make trade-offs between ecosystem service benefits and costs explicit. Monetary valuation translates ecological functions into economic terms, thereby enabling comparison with other societal priorities (Bateman

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et al., 2011; Kumar, 2012; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA), 2005; Turner et al., 2010). Assigning monetary values supports the identification and potential internalization of externalities through instruments such as compensation schemes or hunting fees (Daily et al., 2009; Häggmark-Svensson et al., 2015; Johnston et al., 2015). While valuation results are inherently sensitive to methodological assumptions, they nonetheless provide an essential basis for designing policies that promote more transparent and equitable cost-sharing among stakeholders (Frey et al., 2021).

Building on these theoretical foundations, this study applies valuation approaches consistent with international accounting standards such as SEEA-EA (United Nations et al., 2021). The analysis combines market price and cost-based primary valuation, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatial allocation by land cover. Cost-based methods are recommended where market data are available, as they reflect real expenditure and opportunity costs borne by stakeholders (Johnston et al., 2015; United Nations et al., 2021). Benefit transfer, despite its limitations, is widely used as a pragmatic alternative when primary data collection is constrained, particularly in policy contexts where timely estimates are needed (Richardson et al., 2015). Finally, spatial disaggregation of values follows established practice in ecosystem accounting (Hein et al., 2020; Oras et al., 2021), enhancing policy relevance by linking services to specific land cover classes. Together, these methods generate monetized, spatially explicit estimates of hunting's provisioning and cultural services, which are indicative rather than definitive but provide important, policy-relevant evidence on the economic significance of hunting and the trade-offs inherent in wildlife governance.

While some countries have conducted national or regional valuations of hunting-related ecosystem services, systematic assessments in the Czech Republic remain rare and fragmented. Internationally, Estonia and Latvia have estimated both provisioning and cultural values at the national level (Baumanis et al., 2011; Oras et al., 2021), and studies in the Netherlands and North America have documented regional and national expenditures on recreational hunting (Remme et al., 2015; Arnett & Southwick, 2015; U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service., 2017; U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service., 2023). In the Czech context, the only comprehensive economic assessment dates back to 2010 (Feuereisel, 2010), while more recent work has addressed narrower questions such as market constraints (Němec et al., 2023) or hunting tourism revenue (Kalábová et al., 2025). This fragmented evidence highlights the need for a national-level, integrated assessment that can inform policy and management.

This study addresses that gap by providing the first comprehensive, national-level valuation of hunting's provisioning and cultural ecosystem services in the Czech Republic. It combines detailed hunter's data with spatial analysis and benefit transfer adjusted from international studies to generate up-to-date, policy-relevant estimates of hunting's societal value. Specifically, the objectives are to (i) estimate the value of these services using market price and cost-based methods and (ii) compare these values with those obtained through benefit transfer. Combining market price and cost-based primary data, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatial allocation using CORINE land cover allows the generation of monetized, spatially explicit estimates, which—though indicative—offer important guidance for policymakers on the economic significance of hunting.

2. Materials and methods

Following established practice in ecosystem service assessment, three valuation approaches were applied: market prices for provisioning services, cost-based methods for recreational services, and benefit transfer as a complementary tool (Bateman et al., 2011; Johnston et al., 2015; United Nations et al., 2021). These methods provide transparent, policy-relevant estimates and are consistent with the SEEA-EA framework. However, each approach entails limitations: market prices

capture only traded components, cost-based measures may misrepresent welfare due to income or market constraints, and transferred values risk bias when applied across ecological or cultural contexts (Turner et al., 2010; Pascual et al., 2017; Richardson et al., 2015; Gren & Kerr, 2022).

2.1. Organization of hunting and game management in the Czech Republic

In the Czech Republic, hunting is regulated by the [Hunting Act, Act No. 449/2001 Coll \(2001\)](#), which defines it both as a set of ecosystem-related activities and as part of national cultural heritage. Hunting is permitted only within recognized hunting grounds, which must consist of at least 500 ha of continuous hunting land (or 50 ha for game reserves). Landowners whose property forms part of a hunting ground must form or join a hunting association to gain hunting rights. As a result, most hunting is organized through associations, which manage 74 % of hunting grounds, primarily through leasing. Hunting grounds are mostly open; fenced areas represent only 2 % of the total. The user of a hunting ground—whether a private individual, legal entity, the state, or a hunting club—must appoint a state-approved game manager. Hunting land covers 87 % of the Czech Republic's area and remains stable. Live game is state property, while dead game belongs to the hunting ground user where it is found.

2.2. Valuation of wild game provision

The provisioning value of wild game meat constitutes a private benefit that accrues primarily to hunters through self-consumption or sales, while also generating secondary economic flows when game enters processing and retail chains. This value was assessed on the basis of observed market prices for game meat and hides, using national statistics and a survey of processing companies. As most Czech hunters either consume or partly sell the game they harvest, the market price represents the opportunity cost and an appropriate measure of the provisioning service of hunting. The following section outlines the procedure applied to quantify these values.

To calculate the value of wild game provision, data on the number of hunted game species, the average purchase weight of the cold body of game species, and the average purchase price of game species in 2023 were used (Table 1). The quantity of hunted game species is published yearly at the national level and for 14 regions of the Czech Republic by the Czech Statistical Office (Czech Statistical Office, 2024a). A market survey determined the average purchase price and average purchase weight of cold bodies of game species. Animals are purchased without heads and extremities. Hence, the price includes the meat price as well as the price of other parts that can be used from the animal's body, e.g., skins. The following species were used in the analysis: red deer (*Cervus elaphus*), sika deer (*Cervus nippon*), fallow deer (*Dama dama*), mouflon (*Ovis aries musimon*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), wild boar (*Sus scrofa*), European hare (*Lepus europaeus*), mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*), and pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*).

Table 1
Description of used data – wild game provision.

Data	Coverage	Source
Quantity of hunted game species (2022/23)	- National level - Regional level (14 regions)	- Forest Management Institute - Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic
Average purchase price of game species without VAT (2022/23)	National level	Market survey – meat processing companies
Average purchase weight of the cold body of game species	National level	Survey – meat processing companies

Source: Author's own compilation.

The value of the ecosystem service of wild game provision was calculated using Eq. (1), derived from the author's own methodological framework.

$$GP = \sum_i^N a_i * b_i * c_i \quad (1)$$

Where a_i is the average purchase weight of a species i , b_i is the average purchase price of a species i , c_i is the number of hunted species i , and N is the number of species analyzed, i.e., 9.

The statistics for the hunted game are available for the hunting year (April-March). The statistics for 2022/23 were labelled as the year 2022 in accordance with the labelling convention used by the Czech Statistical Office. Game purchase prices were obtained from the websites of venison purchasing companies. In addition, these companies were contacted directly to obtain data on the average cold carcass weight of the game. The average price was calculated based on the most commonly reported values. In cases where the cold carcass price varied by shot quality and body weight, the average price for each species was derived from the first category, representing the highest quality grade.

2.3. Valuation of recreational hunting

The recreational value of hunting was quantified through a cost-based approach using data on hunters' expenditures and hunting ground leases. These costs, including land access, equipment, and licenses, represent the price of accessing the recreational hunting service and thus serve as a proxy for its value. Recreational hunting expenditures are borne directly by hunters but also generate income for landowners, local businesses, and service providers, capturing the broader economic activity associated with hunting. Two complementary measures were applied: the first based on the leasing costs of hunting grounds, reflecting the fundamental requirement of land access, and the second based on hunters' annual expenditures, which account for the full range of costs beyond leases.

In 2022, 87 % of Czech hunting grounds were leased, covering 85 % of the total hunting area (Czech Statistical Office, 2024a). As no national register of rental prices exists, data from Forests of the Czech Republic, a state enterprise managing 13 % of the hunting area, were used, and the average rental price per hectare was multiplied by the total hunting area to estimate lease-based value.

In the second approach, the value of recreational hunting services was estimated based on the number of hunters and their average annual hunting-related expenditures, following a methodology similar to that used in Estonia (Oras et al., 2021). Data on the number of hunters were obtained from the Forest Management Institute and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic. Information on average annual expenditures was collected via an online survey in autumn 2023 from all 81 regional and district associations of the Czech-Moravian Hunting Union. This approach provides a more comprehensive estimate, as it captures not only the value of leased hunting grounds but also associated costs such as equipment, clothing, and predator control. The value of recreational hunting was estimated by multiplying the average annual expenditure per hunter by the total number of hunters. Table 2 summarizes the data types and sources used to calculate the value of recreational hunting.

2.4. Spatial allocation of ecosystem service values

The spatial allocation of ecosystem service values followed the SEEA-EA guidance, which recommends linking values to land cover classes to enable integration with natural capital accounts (United Nations et al., 2021). Consistent with established practice in ecosystem accounting (Burkhard et al., 2009; Hein et al., 2020; Maes et al., 2012; Remme et al., 2015; Oras et al., 2021), provisioning and cultural values were distributed across ecosystem types in proportion to their spatial extent. This

Table 2
Description of data used – recreational hunting.

Data	Coverage	Source
Area of hunting grounds	- National level - Regional level (14 regions)	- Forest Management Institute - Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic
Rental price of hunting grounds leased by the Forests of the Czech Republic	Hunting grounds leased by the Forests of the Czech Republic in 2022	Forests of the Czech Republic
Number of holders of valid hunting licenses permanently practicing game management rights	- National level - Regional level (14 regions)	- Forest Management Institute - Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic
Average annual expenditure per hunter	National level	Hunter's survey

Source: Author's own compilation

method was selected because it is rarely possible to identify precisely which ecosystem type provides a particular service: most game species occupy large ranges and rely on heterogeneous landscapes composed of multiple ecosystem types, making their specific contributions difficult to disentangle.

While the Forest Management Institute reports only four broad categories of ecosystems within hunting grounds (agricultural land, forest land, water bodies, and other), a finer level of detail was introduced by using the CORINE Land Cover 2018 map (EEA, 2020). From this dataset, artificial areas were excluded, as hunting grounds do not cover built-up land, while bare rocks and sparsely vegetated areas were omitted due to their limited coverage and negligible role as wildlife habitat.

Provisioning values were then allocated by multiplying the total regional value of harvested game by the proportional area of each ecosystem type, whereas recreational values were derived from average hunters' expenditures and the number of registered hunters in the region. This spatial allocation enables consistent comparison of service values across ecosystem types and regions.

2.5. Benefit transfer

To complement the primary estimates, a benefit transfer was conducted using values from comparable European studies, adjusted for species composition, purchasing power, and inflation. Cross-study comparisons in hunting valuation are complicated by heterogeneous methods (revealed and stated preferences) and reporting units (e.g., per day, per trip, per hunter), which limit direct transferability (Häggmark-Svensson et al., 2015). Meta-regression analyses (Gren & Kerr, 2022; Huber et al., 2018) report values per person per day and were therefore unsuitable, as the present study estimates hunters' total annual expenditures across all activities, including game management. Instead, two sources were selected: Oras et al. (2021) for Estonia and expenditure data from Germany and Austria presented by Ebner (2016), both of which report annual hunting-related expenditures using methods consistent with this analysis.

Provisioning values were estimated through an adjusted unit value transfer from Oras et al. (2021), applying species-specific data on carcass weights, meat prices, and, for red deer, skin prices to Czech hunting harvests. Only species hunted in the Czech Republic (red deer, roe deer, wild boar) were included. Recreational values were estimated using average annual expenditures per hunter from the selected studies, applied to the number of registered hunters in the Czech Republic.

To ensure comparability across countries and years, all monetary values were standardized to U.S. dollars (USD) in 2022 prices. First, original figures were adjusted for inflation using country-specific Consumer Price Indices (OECD, 2025). Second, inflation-adjusted values

were converted into USD using Purchasing Power Parities (PPP) for household final consumption expenditure (OECD, 2025a). This two-step procedure is standard practice in benefit transfer, ensuring that values are expressed on a consistent temporal and spatial basis (Johnston et al., 2015; Richardson et al., 2015).

3. Results

3.1. Valuation of wild game provision

The total value of wild game provision was estimated at CZK 548 million (USD 39.7 million). Wild boar accounted for the largest share of this value, whereas mallard, pheasant, mouflon, and European hare each contributed only 1–2 % of the total (Table 3). The species composition contributing to the overall value was consistent across regions (Fig. 1). The highest total value of hunted game was recorded in the Central Bohemia Region. On a per-hectare basis, the value of wild game provision averaged CZK 79, ranging from CZK 47 in Prague to CZK 119 in the Karlovy Vary Region.

3.2. Valuation of recreational hunting

First, the value of the recreational service was estimated using the rental prices of hunting grounds leased by the Forests of the Czech Republic. Assuming all hunting grounds nationwide were leased at the average per-hectare rate applied by this organization, the total rental value, and thus the estimated value of the recreational ecosystem service, amounted to CZK 2.25 billion.

To ascertain average annual hunting expenditures, online questionnaires were disseminated to all 81 regional and district associations of the Czech-Moravian Hunting Union during the autumn of 2023. A total of 260 responses were collected. However, data cleaning was necessary to ensure data quality. Responses containing erroneous entries or exhibiting implausibly high values were excluded from the analysis. Specifically, one outlier value was removed from each of the following expenditure categories: hunting permit (CZK 1,000,000), weapons and ammunition (CZK 250,000), tools (CZK 240,000), and clothing (CZK 100,000). Furthermore, eleven outliers were removed from the car expenditure category (CZK 1,500,000, CZK 600,000, CZK 580,000, CZK 500,000, CZK 350,000, 3x CZK 300,000, 3x CZK 200,000). These values were deemed implausible given the average income levels of the Czech population (annual average net income per person in 2022 was CZK 259.9 thousand (Czech Statistical Office, 2024b)). It is suspected that respondents may have mistakenly included, for example, the total vehicle value rather than solely operational costs associated with hunting activities.

The exclusion of outliers, while necessary for data quality, introduces a degree of subjectivity and potential bias. The number of excluded values is debatable, and their removal inevitably influences the final expenditure estimates. However, retaining these highly inflated values would have likely resulted in significantly overestimated expenditure

Table 3
Value of the provisioning service of wild game provision in 2022.

	Value (CZK)	Share of the total value of wild game provision
Red Deer	98,323,160	18 %
Sika Deer	23,693,580	4 %
Fallow Deer	64,627,816	12 %
Mouflon	5,224,950	1 %
Roe Deer	106,113,000	19 %
Wild Boar	231,240,100	42 %
European Hare	8,422,750	2 %
Mallard	3,764,599	1 %
Pheasant	6,431,933	1 %
Total	547,841,888	

Source: Author's own compilation.

figures. Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of the data utilized for the valuation of recreational hunting.

The average annual expenditure by hunters was CZK 105,509 (approx. USD 7,649), with a 95 % confidence interval ranging from CZK 90,465 to CZK 120,553 (Table 4). The interval was estimated conservatively based on the combined variability across expenditure categories and the smallest available sample size ($n = 98$). Prior to outlier removal, the average expenditure was CZK 133,981, indicating that extreme values significantly inflated the estimate. The largest portion of spending was on vehicles and infrastructure (20 %), while only 5 % went toward mandatory insurance and membership fees for hunting associations. Spending on equipment accounted for 16 %, followed by expenses related to dogs and predator control (13 %), hunting permits (10 %), and weapons (9 %). Fee-based hunting made up 13 % of total expenditures, and spending on hunting clothing and miscellaneous items accounted for 7 % and 6 %, respectively.

Based on average annual expenditures per hunter, the estimated economic value of the recreational service is CZK 9.33 billion (approx. USD 677 million), with a 95 % confidence interval between CZK 8.01 and 10.67 billion. For clarity, the remainder of this text refers to the point estimate of CZK 9.33 billion.

The estimated economic value of recreational hunting services substantially exceeds that of provisioning services (Table 5). When based on hunters' expenditures, the value of recreational services is approximately 17 times higher than that of provisioning services. Even when using the average hunting ground rental price as a more conservative benchmark, recreational services still generate a value four times greater, underscoring their significant contribution relative to provisioning functions.

3.3. Spatial allocation of ecosystem service values

As the applied method assumes uniform per-area contributions of each ecosystem type to service provision, the estimated values are primarily influenced by the spatial extent of each land cover class. Table 6 presents the resulting distribution of ecosystem service values across ecosystem types. These figures reflect an area-based allocation and do not capture differences in ecological function or cultural significance. For instance, water-related ecosystems such as inland marshes and watercourses show relatively low total values due to their limited spatial coverage, even though their ecological importance may be considerable. This reflects an inherent constraint of using land cover area as the basis for value allocation.

To complement this area-based allocation, regional hunting expenditure data were generalized and visualized using a choropleth map classified by the Jenks natural breaks algorithm (Jenks & Caspall, 1971), which emphasizes meaningful differences between regions. The map highlights clear disparities in the economic significance of hunting, offering an accessible overview of spatial patterns that inform the following comparison of provisioning and recreational services (Fig. 2).

The regional distribution of provisioning and recreational hunting services highlights their distinct underlying drivers. Recreational values, measured by hunters' expenditures, are concentrated in Central and South Bohemia, reflecting the density of hunters and the proximity of major urban centers. Provisioning values, in contrast, are highest in South Moravia and Vysočina, where extensive agricultural and forested landscapes support abundant and diverse game populations. These contrasting patterns show that recreational services are shaped mainly by sociodemographic factors, while provisioning services are governed by ecological and land-use conditions. Recognizing this divergence is important for policy, as it suggests that measures targeting hunting-related benefits must be tailored to both social demand and ecological supply.

Fig. 1. Proportion of the value of each species in each region (CZK 2022 million).Created by the author.

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of data used for the valuation of recreational hunting (values in CZK 2022).

	Min	Max	Average	Standard deviation	95 % confidence interval	Number of answers
Fee hunting	0	300,000	13,737	37,478	8,136–19,338	172
Hunting permit	0	400,000	10,925	35,571	6,267–15,583	224
Compulsory insurance, hunting association membership fee	500	66,000	5,546	10,746	3,860–7,232	156
Weapons and ammunition	0	100,000	9,436	14,761	7,576–11,296	242
Tools (knives, binoculars, traps,...)	0	200,000	16,882	28,906	12,954–20,810	208
Hunting clothes	0	50,000	7,620	8,259	6,548–8,692	228
Car and infrastructure	0	150,000	21,510	27,512	17,815–25,205	213
Dogs, predators	0	250,000	13,460	26,859	9,747–17,173	201
Other	0	120,000	6,393	19,705	2,492–10,294	98
Total			105,509		90,465–120,553	

Source: Author’s own compilation.

3.4. Benefit transfer

The application of the adjusted benefit transfer method, drawing upon data from an Estonian study, resulted in an estimated provisioning service value of USD 133,200,613 for red deer, roe deer, and wild boar. This value was substantially higher than the USD 31,586,083 estimated using data specific to the Czech Republic (Table 7).

The economic value of the recreational hunting service, estimated using a benefit transfer approach, was calculated based on average annual hunter expenditures reported in three European countries: Estonia (Oras et al., 2021), Germany, and Austria (Ebner, 2016). Following adjustments for inflation and conversion to USD, the estimated annual expenditures per hunter were USD 5,079 for Estonia, USD 6,904 for Germany, and USD 6,410 for Austria. These figures were applied to the total number of registered hunters in the Czech Republic to derive a range of estimated values for recreational hunting, from USD 449.5 million to USD 610.9 million, with an average estimate of USD 542.5 million.

Table 8 presents a comparison between these benefit transfer-based estimates and a valuation derived from primary data collected in the Czech Republic. According to national data, the average annual expenditure per hunter was USD 7,649, corresponding to a total recreational hunting value of approximately USD 676.9 million. In contrast, the estimate based on the average expenditure across the three international studies (USD 6,131) yielded a lower total value of USD 542.5

million. This comparison illustrates the potential divergence between locally derived and transferred values and highlights the importance of context-specific data in ecosystem service valuation.

While the provisioning service value estimated via the benefit transfer method was substantially higher than the value derived from primary data (with a ratio of 0.24 between the primary estimate and the benefit transfer estimate), the opposite was observed for recreational services: the benefit transfer approach produced a lower estimate, with the ratio of the primary to transferred value equal to 1.25. These results suggest that even small differences in per-hunter expenditure assumptions can lead to significant shifts in total valuation outcomes, emphasizing the importance of accurate, localized data for ecosystem service assessments.

4. Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first national-level assessment of hunting-related ecosystem services in the Czech Republic that quantifies both provisioning and recreational values. The results confirm that recreational hunting generates far greater economic value than the provision of wild game meat, consistent with evidence from other European contexts. By offering an indicative framework that combines administrative records, survey data, and spatial analysis, the study provides a practical blueprint for countries seeking to operationalize ecosystem service valuation within the SEEA-EA framework.

Table 5
Comparison of provisioning and recreational service values for hunting (values in CZK 2022).

	Provisioning service	Recreational service (hunter expenditures)	Recreational service (rental price)	Recreational / Provisioning service (expenditures)	Recreational / Provisioning service (renting)
Hradec Králové Region	25,864,657	508,975,839	133,775,268	20	5
Pardubice Region	25,008,023	510,663,985	127,745,644	20	5
South Bohemian Region	59,307,491	1,193,413,292	298,837,880	20	5
Liberec Region	19,825,093	335,202,372	90,132,753	17	5
Olomouc Region	36,213,137	641,600,763	154,050,372	18	4
Central Bohemian Region	80,189,603	1,387,761,031	311,627,290	17	4
South Moravian Region	54,109,331	1,010,777,061	207,165,676	19	4
Vysocina Region	40,170,856	802,396,612	202,031,340	20	5
Prague	660,269	27,959,908	4,549,358	42	7
Plzen Region	63,972,246	864,013,920	222,194,941	14	3
Usti nad Labem Region	46,962,904	555,083,311	141,155,673	12	3
Karlovy Vary Region	34,918,403	235,390,775	95,811,849	7	3
Moravian-Silesian Region	32,693,534	633,793,090	149,841,406	19	5
Zlin Region	27,946,345	629,361,708	114,431,421	23	4
Total Czech Republic	547,841,888	9,336,393,666	2,253,350,872	17	4

Source: Author's own compilation.

Table 6
Ecosystem service value of provisioning wild game and recreational hunting by ecosystem types (values in CZK 2022).

	Value of provisioning service	Value of recreational service
Agricultural areas		
Non-irrigated arable land	213,646,436	3,640,990,725
Vineyards	1,258,719	21,451,256
Fruit trees and berry plantations	1,955,652	33,328,487
Pastures	60,044,840	1,023,292,079
Complex cultivation patterns	3,518,857	59,968,828
Land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation	53,062,110	904,291,467
Forest and seminatural areas		
Broad-leaved forest	21,089,788	359,414,952
Coniferous forest	123,970,444	2,112,720,651
Mixed forest	47,903,863	816,383,947
Natural grasslands	1,872,895	31,918,125
Moors and heathland	168,036	2,863,695
Transitional woodland-shrub	14,223,149	242,392,777
Wetlands		
Inland marshes	454,000	7,737,136
Peat bogs	339,868	5,792,069
Water bodies		
Water courses	343,197	5,848,806
Water bodies	3,990,033	67,998,667
Total Czech Republic	547,841,888	9,336,393,666

Source: Author's own compilation

The recreational hunting values reported here are broadly in line with international findings but also reveal substantial cross-country variation. For example, [Baumanis et al. \(2011\)](#) estimated a recreational-to-provisioning ratio of 5.2 in Latvia, comparable to the Czech estimates ranging from 4 (leasing costs) to 17 (hunter expenditures). Yet Czech hunters reported annual expenditures of about USD 7,649, far above the USD 2,136 in Latvia or the USD 2,237–2,708 found in recent U.S. surveys (U.S. Department of the Interior, 2017; 2023). These differences likely reflect variations in income, hunting practices, and the scope of included costs. [Remme et al. \(2015\)](#), for instance, reported far lower values for the Netherlands when based only on hunting

rights (USD 8–63/ha), compared to USD 92/ha in this study.

The Czech analysis also improves on earlier domestic studies by collecting detailed expenditure data across a wide range of categories. This includes not only equipment and hunting rights, but also infrastructure, predator control, and vehicle costs, providing a more comprehensive picture of actual spending than many international studies. The Estonian valuation ([Oras et al., 2021](#)), for example, was based on a limited number of hunter interviews and may not fully capture the diversity of expenditure patterns. Compared with [Feuer-eisel's \(2010\)](#) pioneering Czech assessment, the present study reports higher expenditures, but once adjusted for inflation and omitted categories such as hunting dogs, the results converge. More recent Czech work has addressed narrower questions, such as market constraints ([Němec et al., 2023](#)) or sectoral impacts ([Kalábová, 2023](#)), but lacked a full valuation framework.

The comparison of valuation approaches underscores the risks of relying solely on transferred values. For provisioning, benefit transfer produced estimates more than four times higher than primary data, reflecting both price differences and broader cost assumptions in the Estonian study, such as the inclusion of skin values. By contrast, the recreational transfer was 25 % lower than Czech survey data, pointing to variation in practices, expenditure structures, and cultural contexts. Although this study adjusted transferred values, these divergences highlight the limits of transferability and the importance of local calibration.

Addressing the generalization bias of transferred point values was also a methodological priority. To reduce this bias ([Johnston et al., 2015](#); [Richardson et al., 2015](#)), transferred estimates were adjusted for species composition, inflation, and purchasing power, and were complemented by reporting confidence intervals and alternative valuation approaches (hunter expenditures vs. leasing costs). These steps cannot fully eliminate transfer-related uncertainties, but they improve transparency and robustness, ensuring that policy conclusions do not rest on unadjusted point estimates alone.

Methodologically, this study advances ecosystem service valuation by integrating market price and cost-based primary data, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatially explicit disaggregation by land cover type. Consistent with SEEA-EA guidance and the approach of [Oras et al. \(2021\)](#), this design allows a more precise attribution of both

Fig. 2. Regional distribution of provisioning (left) and recreational hunting services (right, based on hunters' expenditures) in the Czech Republic. Source: Author's own elaboration based on survey data, created in Inkscape.

Table 7

Comparison of the value of provisioning service based on the primary study and benefit transfer (values in 2022 USD).

	Primary study	Benefit transfer	Primary study/benefit transfer
Red deer	7,128,329	15,467,118	0.46
European roe deer	7,693,084	12,000,159	0.64
Wild boar	16,764,671	105,733,336	0.16
Total	31,586,083	133,200,613	0.24

Source: Author's own compilation.

Table 8

Comparison of annual recreational hunting values per hunter and total estimated values based on primary data from the Czech Republic and benefit transfer from Estonia, Germany, and Austria (values in 2022 USD).

Country	Annual hunter expenditure per capita	Value of the recreational service in the Czech Republic	Source	Primary study/benefit transfer
Czech Republic (primary study)	7,649	676,878,993	Present study	1
Czech Republic (benefit transfer)	6,131	542,545,960	Present study	1.25
Estonia	5,079	449,473,906	Oras et al. (2021)	1.51
Germany	6,904	610,914,584	Ebner (2016)	1.11
Austria	6,410	567,249,391	Ebner (2016)	1.19

Source: Author's own compilation.

provisioning and cultural values across regions and ecosystems. The spatial perspective enhances policy relevance—for example, in targeting wildlife management or designing compensation schemes—yet also highlights limitations. Assuming uniform per-area contributions overlooks ecological variation and calls for more refined allocation methods in future research. Importantly, the results demonstrate the significant, yet often underrepresented, role of recreational hunting as a cultural service.

Beyond the Czech case, this analysis represents one of the first comprehensive national-level assessments of hunting-related services in Central Europe. While the monetary estimates should be interpreted cautiously, they contribute to international efforts to operationalize

both provisioning and cultural services within natural capital accounts. The dual-method design also facilitates systematic comparison of valuation techniques, illustrating how benefit transfer, even when methodologically aligned, can diverge substantially from primary data. Combining approaches, therefore, improves robustness, especially in contexts where primary valuation remains scarce.

Finally, interpreting these values requires attention to stakeholder perspectives. The benefits and costs of hunting are distributed unevenly: wild meat primarily benefits hunters, lease payments accrue to landowners and hunting associations, and recreational expenditures generate wider economic flows through local businesses and rural communities. At the same time, game-related damages are often externalized to landowners and the public. Recognizing these distributional dimensions is crucial for designing fair and effective policies, ensuring that ecosystem service valuation informs not only aggregate accounting but also equitable management of hunting-related services.

4.1. Limitations and future directions

This study provides the first integrated national-level assessment of hunting-related ecosystem services in the Czech Republic, but several limitations must be acknowledged. The estimation of recreational value relied on self-reported expenditure data from an online survey of 260 hunters. While this represents a substantial dataset, the non-random sampling via hunting associations may have introduced self-selection bias toward more active or higher-spending hunters. Potential misreporting also cannot be excluded—for example, some respondents may have reported the full purchase price of equipment or vehicles rather than annualized costs. Although extreme outliers were removed to improve data quality, such exclusions involve subjective judgement and may have influenced aggregate estimates.

Further limitations arise from the valuation methods. The spatial allocation approach followed SEEA-EA guidance and established practice in ecosystem accounting (United Nations et al., 2021; Remme et al., 2015; Oras et al., 2021), but its simplifying assumption of uniform per-area contributions highlights the need for more ecologically detailed allocation methods in future work. The benefit transfer relied on values from other European countries with different institutional and cultural contexts, limiting comparability despite adjustments for species composition, inflation, and purchasing power. In addition, the analysis covered only provisioning and recreational services. Non-use and indirect values, such as biodiversity conservation or cultural heritage, were excluded, likely leading to underestimation. Some overlap between provisioning and recreational components is also possible, as willingness to pay for access may reflect expectations of meat harvest, and meat prices may embody cultural perceptions of hunting.

Another important omission concerns regulating services. Hunting contributes to reducing crop and forest damage by controlling ungulate

populations, particularly red deer, roe deer, and wild boar. The extent of this regulatory function depends on harvest intensity, culling structure, and regional population dynamics (Apollonio et al., 2017). In some contexts, the avoided damage costs may rival or exceed provisioning values, but robust quantification would require integrated ecological and economic modelling. Extending the framework to incorporate such regulating services represents a key direction for future research.

These limitations highlight priorities for advancing research. More representative data collection—ideally with stratified sampling by region, age, and hunting activity—would reduce bias. Developing ecologically detailed allocation methods would allow spatial patterns of hunting services to reflect habitat quality and management effort more accurately. Broader valuation, including non-use, indirect, and regulating services, alongside clearer separation of provisioning and recreational components, would provide a more comprehensive assessment. Within these constraints, the present study should be viewed not as a definitive valuation but as an indicative methodological framework. Its main contribution lies in demonstrating how cost-based primary data, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatial allocation can be integrated within the SEEA-EA to capture underrepresented cultural services such as recreational hunting. While monetary estimates should be interpreted with caution, the study offers methodological insights and empirical evidence that can inform both national policy and international efforts to embed cultural and provisioning services in natural capital accounting.

5. Conclusion

This study provides the first comprehensive, national-level valuation of both provisioning and recreational ecosystem services associated with hunting in the Czech Republic. The results show that recreational hunting generates substantially greater economic value than the market value of wild game, by a factor ranging from four to seventeen, depending on the valuation method. This highlights the need for natural capital accounting and land-use policies to recognize not only material outputs but also the high cultural and recreational value of wildlife-based activities.

By integrating cost-based valuation, adjusted benefit transfer, and spatial allocation using CORINE land cover data, this study operationalizes key principles of the SEEA-EA framework. The results offer practical insights for incorporating hunting-related services into national ecosystem accounts. Importantly, the comparison between primary data and benefit transfer reveals notable discrepancies, underscoring the importance of locally specific data to avoid misestimation in ecosystem service valuation.

The findings may serve as a basis for policy instruments aimed at balancing the uneven distribution of costs and benefits associated with hunting. One possible avenue is the development of compensation mechanisms or Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), which have been applied in other contexts to align the interests of landowners, hunters, and the public (Frey et al., 2021). While the detailed design of PES schemes was beyond the scope of this study, the valuation results provide evidence that can support such policy debates in the Czech Republic.

The approach applied here is scalable and adaptable to other EU countries with comparable data infrastructures and policy ambitions. While the monetary estimates should be interpreted as indicative, the study demonstrates a methodological framework that can be replicated in principle and refined through more systematic and stratified data collection, thereby supporting ecosystem accounting and wildlife management across Europe.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eva Horváthová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The author declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data and calculations used in this study are available at Horvathova, Eva (2025), “HuntingCzechRepublic”, Mendeley Data, V1, doi: 10.17632/v9c7xt3vsf.1

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